

MORELLO, Thais Laham. **O búfalo que só queria ficar abraçado** [The buffalo who only wants to be cuddled]. Illustrations Juliana Basile. São Paulo: Carochinha, 2018.

REVIEW¹

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Young duo Thais Laham Morello and Juliana Basile bring a light-hearted and nicely-illustrated book about a needy buffalo who wants to be cuddled all the time. He plays all day long but, once he feels sleepy, he wants his mother to hold him. At school, it is no different – he is nothing but a lovesick buffalo. Until, one day, his mother comes up with an idea to help him.

Keywords: Affection. Emotions. Relationship.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2019 Bologna. Books published in 2018 and reviewed in 2019. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

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